

Rough Standard Neutrosophic Sets: An Application on Standard Neutrosophic Information Systems

Nguyen Xuan Thao¹, Bui Cong Cuong², Florentin Smarandache³

¹Faculty of Information Technology, Vietnam National University of Agriculture. E-mail: nxthao2000@gmail.com

²Institute of Mathematics, Vietnam Academy of Science and Technology, 18 Hoang Quoc Viet, Hanoi, Vietnam. E-mail: bccuong@gmail.com

³Department of Mathematics, University of New Mexico, 705 Gurley Avenue, Gallup, NM 87301, USA. E-mail: smarand@unm.edu

Abstract: A rough fuzzy set is the result of the approximation of a fuzzy set with respect to a crisp approximation space. It is a mathematical tool for the knowledge discovery in the fuzzy information systems. In this paper, we introduce the concepts of rough standard

neutrosophic sets and standard neutrosophic information system, and give some results of the knowledge discovery on standard neutrosophic information system based on rough standard neutrosophic sets.

Keywords: rough set, standard neutrosophic set, rough standard neutrosophic set, standard neutrosophic information systems

1 Introduction

Rough set theory was introduced by Z. Pawlak in 1980s [1]. It became a useful mathematical tool for data mining, especially for redundant and uncertain data. At first, the establishment of the rough set theory is based on the equivalence relation. The set of equivalence classes of the universal set, obtained by an equivalence relation, is the basis for the construction of upper and lower approximation of the subset of universal set.

Fuzzy set theory was introduced by L. Zadeh since 1965 [2]. Immediately, it became a useful method to study in the problems of imprecision and uncertainty. Ever since, a lot of new theories treating imprecision and uncertainty have been introduced. For instance, intuitionistic fuzzy sets were introduced in 1986, by K. Atanassov [3], which is a generalization of the notion of a fuzzy set. While the fuzzy set gives the degree of membership of an element in a given set, intuitionistic fuzzy set gives a degree of membership and a degree of non-membership of an element in a given set. In 1999 [17], F. Smarandache introduced the concept of neutrosophic set which generalized fuzzy set and intuitionistic fuzzy set. It is a set in which each proposition is estimated to have a degree of truth (T), a degree of indeterminacy (I) and a degree of falsity (F). After a while, the subclass of neutrosophic sets was proposed. They are more advantageous in the practical application. Wang et al. [18] proposed the interval neutrosophic sets, and some of their operators. Smarandache [17] and Wang et al. [19] introduced a single valued neutrosophic set as an instance of

the neutrosophic set accompanied with various set theoretic operators and properties. Ye [20] defined the concept of simplified neutrosophic set. It is a set where each element of the universe has a degree of truth, indeterminacy and falsity respectively, stretching between $[0, 1]$. Ye also suggested some operational laws for simplified neutrosophic sets, and two aggregation operators, including a simplified neutrosophic weighted arithmetic average operator and a simplified neutrosophic weighted geometric average operator.

In 2013, B.C. Cuong and V. Kreinovich introduced the concept of picture fuzzy set [4, 5], in which a given set has three memberships: a degree of positive membership, a degree of negative membership, and a degree of neutral membership of an element in this set. After that, L. H. Son gave the application of the picture fuzzy set in the clustering problems [7, 8]. We regard picture fuzzy sets as particular cases of the standard neutrosophic sets [6].

In addition, combining rough set and fuzzy set enhanced many interesting results. The approximation of rough (or fuzzy) sets in fuzzy approximation space give us the fuzzy rough set [9,10,11]; and the approximation of fuzzy sets in crisp approximation space give us the rough fuzzy set [9,10]. W. Z. Wu et al. [11] presented a general framework for the study of the fuzzy rough sets in both constructive and axiomatic approaches. Moreover, W. Z. Wu and Y. H. Xu investigated the fuzzy topological structures on the rough fuzzy sets [12], in which both constructive and axiomatic approaches are used. In 2012, Y. H. Xu and W. Z. Wu investigated the rough intuitionistic

fuzzy set and the intuitionistic fuzzy topologies in crisp approximation spaces [13]. In 2013, B. Davvaz and M. Jafarzadeh studied the rough intuitionistic fuzzy information system [14]. In 2014, X. T. Nguyen introduced the rough picture fuzzy sets. It is the result of approximation of a picture fuzzy set with respect to a crisp approximation space [15].

In this paper, we introduce the concept of standard neutrosophic information system, and study some problems of the knowledge discovery of standard neutrosophic information system based on rough standard neutrosophic sets. The remaining part of this paper is organized as follows: we recall the basic notions of rough set, standard neutrosophic set and rough standard neutrosophic set on the crisp approximation space, respectively, in Sections 2 and 3. In Section 4, we introduce the basic concepts of standard neutrosophic information system. Finally, we investigate some problems of the knowledge discovery of standard neutrosophic information system: the knowledge reduction and extension of the standard neutrosophic information system, in Section 5 and Section 6, respectively.

2 Basic notions of standard neutrosophic set and rough set

In this paper, we denote by U a nonempty set called the universe of discourse. The class of all subsets of U will be denoted by P(U) and the class of all fuzzy subsets of U will be denoted by F(U).

Definition 1. [6]. A standard neutrosophic (PF) set A on the universe U is an object of the form

$$A = \{(x, \mu_A(x), \eta_A(x), \gamma_A(x)) \mid x \in U\}$$

where $\mu_A(x) (\in [0,1])$ is called the “degree of positive membership of x in A”, $\eta_A(x) (\in [0,1])$ is called the “degree of neutral membership of x in A” and $\gamma_A(x) (\in [0,1])$ is called the “degree of negative membership of x in A”, where μ_A, η_A, γ_A and μ_A, η_A, γ_A satisfy the following condition:

$$\mu_A(x) + \eta_A(x) + \gamma_A(x) \leq 1, (\forall x \in X) \mu_A(x) + \gamma_A(x) + \eta_A(x) \leq 1, (\forall x \in X).$$

The family of all standard neutrosophic set in U is denoted by PFS(U). The complement of a picture fuzzy set A is

$$\sim A = \{(x, \gamma_A(x), \eta_A(x), \mu_A(x)) \mid \forall x \in U\}.$$

Obviously, any intuitionistic fuzzy set:

$$A = \{(x, \mu_A(x), \gamma_A(x))\}$$

may be identified with the standard neutrosophic set in the form

$$A = \{(x, \mu_A(x), 0, \gamma_A(x)) \mid x \in U\}$$

$$A = \{(x, \mu_A(x), \gamma_A(x), 0) \mid x \in U\}.$$

The operators on PFS(U): $A \subseteq B, A \cap B, A \cup B$ were introduced in [4].

Now we define some special PF sets: a constant PF set is the PF set $(\overline{\alpha}, \overline{\beta}, \overline{\theta}) = \{(x, \alpha, \beta, \theta) \mid x \in U\}$; the PF universe set is $U = 1_U = (\overline{1}, \overline{0}, \overline{0}) = \{(x, 1, 0, 0) \mid x \in U\}$ and the PF empty set is $\emptyset = 0_U = (\overline{0}, \overline{0}, \overline{1}) = \{(x, 0, 0, 1) \mid x \in U\}$ $\emptyset = 0_U = (\overline{0}, \overline{1}, \overline{0}) = \{(x, 0, 1, 0) \mid x \in U\}$.

For any $x \in U$, standard neutrosophic set 1_x and $1_{U-\{x\}}$ are, respectively, defined by: for all $y \in U$

$$\mu_{1_x}(y) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } y = x \\ 0 & \text{if } y \neq x \end{cases}, \eta_{1_x}(y) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } y = x \\ 0 & \text{if } y \neq x \end{cases},$$

$$\gamma_{1_x}(y) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } y = x \\ 1 & \text{if } y \neq x \end{cases}, \mu_{1_{U-\{x\}}}(y) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } y = x \\ 1 & \text{if } y \neq x \end{cases},$$

$$\eta_{1_{U-\{x\}}}(y) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } y = x \\ 0 & \text{if } y \neq x \end{cases}, \gamma_{1_{U-\{x\}}}(y) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } y = x \\ 0 & \text{if } y \neq x \end{cases}$$

Definition 2. (Lattice $(D^*, \leq_{D^*})$). Let

$$D^* = \{(x_1, x_2, x_3) \in [0,1]^3 : x_1 + x_2 + x_3 \leq 1\}.$$

We define a relation $\leq_{D^*}$ on D^* as follows:

$$\forall (x_1, x_2, x_3), (y_1, y_2, y_3) \in D^*$$

then

$$(x_1, x_2, x_3) \leq_{D^*} (y_1, y_2, y_3) \iff (x_1, x_2, x_3) \leq_{D^*} (y_1, y_2, y_3)$$

if only if

$$(\text{or } (x_1 < y_1, x_3 \geq y_3) (x_1 < y_1, x_3 \geq y_3) \text{ or } (x_1 =$$

$$y_1, x_3 > y_3) (x = x', y > y')$$

$$\text{or } (x_1 = y_1, x_3 = y_3, x_2 \leq y_2) (x = x', y = y', z \leq z'))$$

$$\text{and } (x_1, x_2, x_3) =_{D^*} (y_1, y_2, y_3) \iff (x_1 = y_1, x_2 = y_2, x_3 = y_3).$$

We have $(D^*, \leq_{D^*})$ is a lattice. Denote $0_{D^*} = (0,0,1), 1_{D^*} = (1,0,0)$ Now, we define some operators on D^* .

Definition 3.

- (i) Negative of $x = (x_1, x_2, x_3) \in D^*$ is $\bar{x} = (x_3, x_2, x_1)$
- (ii) For all $x = (x_1, x_2, x_3) \in D^*$ we have $x \wedge y = (x_1 \wedge y_1, x_2 \wedge y_2, x_3 \vee y_3)$
 $x \vee y = (x_1 \vee y_1, x_2 \wedge y_2, x_3 \wedge y_3).$

We have some properties of those operators.

Lemma 1.

(a) For all $x = (x_1, x_2, x_3) \in D^*$ we have

$$(b1) \overline{x \wedge y} = \overline{x} \vee \overline{y} \quad \overline{x \vee y} = \overline{x} \wedge \overline{y}$$

$$(b2) \overline{x \wedge y} = \overline{x} \wedge \overline{y} \quad \overline{x \vee y} = \overline{x} \vee \overline{y}$$

(b) For all $x, y, u, v \in D^*$ and $x \leq_{D^*} u, y \leq_{D^*} v$ we have

$$(c1) x \wedge y \leq_{D^*} u \wedge v$$

$$(c2) x \vee y \leq_{D^*} u \vee v$$

Proof.

(a) We have $\overline{x \wedge y} = (x_3 \vee y_3, x_2 \wedge y_2, x_1 \wedge y_1) = (x_3, x_2, x_1) \vee (y_3, y_2, y_1) = \overline{x} \vee \overline{y}$

Similarly $\overline{x \vee y} = (x_3 \wedge y_3, x_2 \wedge y_2, x_1 \vee y_1) = (x_3, x_2, x_1) \wedge (y_3, y_2, y_1) = \overline{x} \wedge \overline{y}$

(b) For $a, b, c, d \in [0, 1]$, if $a \leq b, c \leq d$ then $a \wedge c \leq b \wedge d$ and. From definitions 2 and 3, we have the result to prove. $\square$

Now, we mention the level sets of the standard neutrosophic sets, where $(\alpha, \beta, \theta) \in D^*$; we define:

• (α, β, θ) - level cut set of the standard neutrosophic set $A = \{(x, \mu_A(x), \eta_A(x), \gamma_A(x)) \mid x \in U\}$

$A = \{(x, \mu_A(x), \gamma_A(x), \eta_A(x)) \mid x \in U\}$ as follows:

$$A_{\theta}^{\alpha, \beta} = \{x \in U \mid (\mu_A(x), \eta_A(x), \gamma_A(x)) \geq (\alpha, \beta, \theta)\} = \{x \in U \mid (\mu_A(x), \eta_A(x), \gamma_A(x)) \geq (\alpha, \beta, \theta)\}$$

• strong (α, β, θ) - level cut set of the standard neutrosophic set A as follows:

$$A_{\theta^+}^{\alpha, \beta} = \{x \in U \mid (\mu_A(x), \eta_A(x), \gamma_A(x)) > (\alpha, \beta, \theta)\}$$

• $(\alpha^+, \beta, \theta)$ -- level cut set of the standard neutrosophic set A as

$$A_{\theta}^{\alpha^+, \beta} = \{x \in U \mid \mu_A(x) > \alpha, \gamma_A(x) \leq \theta\}$$

• $(\alpha, \beta, \theta^+)$ – level cut set of the standard neutrosophic set A as

$$A_{\theta^+}^{\alpha, \beta} = \{x \in U \mid \mu_A(x) \geq \alpha, \gamma_A(x) < \theta\}$$

By $\beta = 0$ we denoted

$$A_{\theta}^{\alpha} = A_{\theta}^{\alpha, 0}$$

• (α^+, θ^+) - level cut set of the standard neutrosophic set A as

$$A_{\theta^+}^{\alpha^+} = \{x \in U \mid \mu_A(x) > \alpha, \gamma_A(x) < \theta\}$$

• α - level cut set of the degree of positive membership of x in A as

$$A^{\alpha} = \{x \in U \mid \mu_A(x) \geq \alpha\}$$

the strong α - level cut set of the degree of positive membership of x in A as

$$A^{\alpha^+} = \{x \in U \mid \mu_A(x) > \alpha\}$$

• θ - level low cut set of the degree of negative membership of x in A as

$$A_{\theta} = \{x \in U \mid \gamma_A(x) \leq \theta\}$$

the strong θ - level low cut set of the degree of negative membership of x in A as

$$A_{\theta^+} = \{x \in U \mid \gamma_A(x) < \theta\}$$

Example 1. Given the universe $U = \{u_1, u_2, u_3\}$. Then $A = ((u_1, 0.8, 0.05, 0.1), (u_2, 0.7, 0.1, 0.2), (u_3, 0.5, 0.01, 0.4))$ is a standard neutrosophic set on U . Then $A_{0.1}^{0.7, 0.2} = \{u_1, u_2\}$ but $A_{0.1}^{0.7, 0.1} = \{u_1\}$ and $A_{0.1^+}^{0.7, 0.2} = \{u_1\}$, $A_{0.1}^{0.7} = \{u_1\}$, $A_{0.1^+}^{0.7} = \emptyset$, $A^{0.5} = \{u_1, u_2, u_3\}$, $A^{0.5^+} = \{u_1, u_2\}$, $A_{0.2^+} = \{u_1\}$, $A_{0.2} = \{u_1, u_2\}$.

Definition 3. Let U be a nonempty universe of discourse which may be infinite. A subset $R \in P(U \times U)$ is referred to as a (crisp) binary relation on U . The relation R is referred to as:

• Reflexive: if for all $x \in U$, $(x, x) \in R$.

• Symmetric: if for all $x, y \in U$, $(x, y) \in R \implies (y, x) \in R$.

• Transitive: if for all $x, y, z \in U$, $(x, y) \in R, (y, z) \in R \implies (x, z) \in R$.

• Similarity: if R is reflexive and symmetric

• Preorder: if R is reflexive and transitive

• Equivalence: if R is reflexive and symmetric, transitive.

A crisp approximation space is a pair (U, R) . For an arbitrary crisp relation R on U , we can define a set-valued mapping $R_s : U \rightarrow P(U)$ by:

$$R_s(x) = \{y \in U \mid (x, y) \in R\}, x \in U.$$

Then, $R_s(x)$ is called the successor neighborhood of x with respect to (w.r.t) R .

Definition 4.[9]. Let (U, R) be a crisp approximation space. For each crisp set $A \subseteq U$, we define the upper and lower approximations of A (w.r.t) (U, R) denoted by $\bar{R}(A)$ and $\underline{R}(A)$, respectively, are defined as follows:

$$\bar{R}(A) = \{x \in U : R_s(x) \cap A \neq \emptyset\},$$

$$\underline{R}(A) = \{x \in U : R_s(x) \subseteq A\}$$

$U : R_s(x) \subseteq A\}$.

Remark 2.1. Let (U, R) be a Pawlak approximation space, i.e. R is an equivalence relation. Then $R_s(x) = [x]_R$ holds. For each crisp set $A \subseteq U$, the upper and lower approximations of A (w.r.t) (U, R) denoted by $\bar{R}(A)$ and $\underline{R}(A)$, respectively, are defined as follows:

$$\bar{R}(A) = \{x \in U : [x]_R \cap A \neq \emptyset\} \quad \underline{R}(A) = \{x \in U : [x]_R \subseteq A\}$$

Definition 5. [16] Let (U, R) be a crisp approximation space. For each fuzzy set $A \subseteq U$, we define the upper and lower approximations of A (w.r.t) (U, R) denoted by $\bar{R}(A)$ and $\underline{R}(A)$, respectively, are defined as follows:

$$\bar{R}(A) = \{x \in U : R_s(x) \cap A \neq \emptyset\},$$

$$\underline{R}(A) = \{x \in U : R_s(x) \subseteq A\}$$

where

$$\mu_{\bar{R}(A)}(x) = \max\{\mu_A(y) \mid y \in R_s(x)\},$$

$$\mu_{\underline{R}(A)}(x) = \min\{\mu_A(y) \mid y \in R_s(x)\}$$

Remark 2.2. Let (U, R) be a Pawlak approximation space, i.e. R is an equivalence relation. Then $R_s(x) = [x]_R$ holds. For each fuzzy set $A \subseteq U$, the upper and lower approximations of A (w.r.t) (U, R) denoted by $\bar{R}(A)$ and $\underline{R}(A)$, respectively, are defined as follows:

$$\bar{R}(A) = \{x \in U : [x]_R \cap A \neq \emptyset\},$$

$$\underline{R}(A) = \{x \in U : [x]_R \subseteq A\}$$

This is the rough fuzzy set in [6].

3. Rough standard neutrosophic set

A rough standard neutrosophic set is the approximation of a standard neutrosophic set w. r. t a crisp approximation space. Here, we consider the upper and lower approximations of a standard neutrosophic set in the crisp approximation spaces together with their membership functions, respectively.

Definition 5: Let (U, R) be a crisp approximation space. For $A \in PFS(U)$, the upper and lower approximations of A (w.r.t) (U, R) denoted by $\bar{RP}(A)$ and $\underline{RP}(A)$, respectively, are defined as follows:

$$\bar{RP}(A) = \{(x, \mu_{\bar{RP}(A)}(x), \eta_{\bar{RP}(A)}(x), \gamma_{\bar{RP}(A)}(x)) \mid x \in U\}$$

$$\underline{RP}(A) = \{(x, \mu_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x), \eta_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x), \gamma_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x)) \mid x \in U\}$$

where

$$\mu_{\bar{RP}(A)}(x) = \bigvee_{y \in R_s(x)} \mu_A(y), \quad \eta_{\bar{RP}(A)}(x) = \bigwedge_{y \in R_s(x)} \eta_A(y),$$

$$\underline{RP}(A) = \{(x, \mu_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x), \eta_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x), \gamma_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x)) \mid x \in U\},$$

and

$$\underline{RP}(A) = \{(x, \mu_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x), \eta_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x), \gamma_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x)) \mid x \in U\},$$

$$\eta_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x) = \bigwedge_{y \in R_s(x)} \eta_A(y), \quad \gamma_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x) = \bigvee_{y \in R_s(x)} \gamma_A(y).$$

$$\underline{RP}(A) = \{(x, \mu_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x), \eta_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x), \gamma_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x)) \mid x \in U\}$$

We have $\bar{RP}(A)$ and $\underline{RP}(A)$, two standard neutrosophic sets in U . Indeed, for each $x \in U$, for all $\epsilon > 0$, it exists $y_0 \in U$ such that $\mu_{\bar{RP}(A)}(x) - \epsilon \leq \mu_A(y_0) \leq \mu_{\bar{RP}(A)}(x)$, $\eta_{\bar{RP}(A)}(x) \leq \eta_A(y_0)$, $\gamma_{\bar{RP}(A)}(x) \leq \gamma_A(y_0)$

$$\text{so that } \mu_{\bar{RP}(A)}(x) - \epsilon + \eta_{\bar{RP}(A)}(x) + \gamma_{\bar{RP}(A)}(x)$$

$$\leq \mu_A(y_0) + \eta_A(y_0) + \gamma_A(y_0) \leq 1$$

$$\mu_{\bar{RP}(A)}(x) - \epsilon + \eta_{\bar{RP}(A)}(x) + \gamma_{\bar{RP}(A)}(x) \leq 1$$

Hence $\mu_{\bar{RP}(A)}(x) + \eta_{\bar{RP}(A)}(x) + \gamma_{\bar{RP}(A)}(x) \leq 1 + \epsilon$, for all $\epsilon > 0$. It means that $\bar{RP}(A)$ is a standard neutrosophic set. By the same way, we obtain $\underline{RP}(A)$ a standard neutrosophic set. Moreover, $\underline{RP}(A) \subset \bar{RP}(A)$.

Thus, the standard neutrosophic mappings $\bar{RP}, \underline{RP} : PFS(U) \rightarrow PFS(U)$ are referred to as the upper and lower PF approximation operators, respectively, and the pair $PR(A) = (\underline{RP}(A), \bar{RP}(A))$ is called the rough standard

neutrosophic set of A w.r.t the approximation space. The picture fuzzy set denoted by $\sim RP(A)$ and is defined by $\sim PR(A) = (\sim \underline{PR}(A), \sim \overline{RP}(A))$ where $\sim \underline{RP}(A)$ and $\sim \overline{RP}(A)$ are the complements of the PF sets $\overline{RP}(A)$ and $\underline{RP}(A)$ respectively.

Example 2. We consider the universe set $U = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4, u_5\}$ and a binary relation R on U in Table 1. Here, if $u_i R u_j$ then cell (i, j) takes a value of 1, cell (i, j) takes a value of 0 (i, j = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5). A standard neutrosophic

$$A = \{(u_1, 0.7, 0.1, 0.2), (u_2, 0.6, 0.2, 0.1), (u_3, 0.6, 0.2, 0.05), (u_4, 0.6, 0.2, 0.1), (u_5, 0.6, 0.2, 0.05)\}$$

Table 1: Binary relation R on U

R	u_1	u_2	u_3	u_4	u_5
u_1	1	0	1	0	0
u_2	0	1	0	1	1
u_3	1	0	1	0	1
u_4	0	1	0	1	0
u_5	0	0	1	1	1

We have $R_s(u_1) = \{u_1, u_3\}$, $R_s(u_2) = \{u_2, u_4, u_5\}$,

$R_s(u_3) = \{u_1, u_3, u_5\}$, $R_s(u_4) = \{u_2, u_4\}$,

$R_s(u_5) = \{u_3, u_4, u_5\}$ $R_s(u_5) = \{u_3, u_4, u_5\}$.

Therefore, we obtain the results

$$\mu_{\overline{RP}(A)}(u_1) = \bigvee_{y \in R_s(u_1)} \mu_A(y)$$

$$\mu_{\overline{RP}(A)}(u_1) = \bigvee_{y \in R_s(u_1)} \mu_A(y) = \max\{\mu_A(u_1), \mu_A(u_3)\}$$

$$= \max\{0.7, 0.6\} = 0.7,$$

$$\eta_{\underline{RP}(A)}(u_1) = \bigwedge_{y \in R_s(u_1)} \eta_A(y) = \min\{\eta_A(u_1), \eta_A(u_3)\}$$

$$= \max\{0.7, 0.6\} = 0.7,$$

$$\gamma_{\underline{RP}(A)}(u_1) = \bigwedge_{y \in R_s(u_1)} \gamma_A(y) = \min\{\gamma_A(u_1), \gamma_A(u_3)\}$$

$$\gamma_{\underline{RP}(A)}(u_1) = \bigwedge_{y \in R_s(u_1)} \gamma_A(y) = \min\{\gamma_A(u_1), \gamma_A(u_3)\} = \max\{0.7, 0.6\} = 0.7 \min\{0.2, 0.05\} = 0.05$$

Similar calculations for other elements of U, we have upper approximations of A

$$\overline{RP}(A) = \{(u_1, 0.7, 0.1, 0.05), (u_2, 0.6, 0.2, 0.1),$$

$$(u_3, 0.7, 0.1, 0.05), (u_4, 0.6, 0.2, 0.1), (u_5, 0.6, 0.2, 0.05)\}$$

and lower approximations of A is

$$\underline{RP}(A) = \{(u_1, 0.6, 0.1, 0.2), (u_2, 0.4, 0.2, 0.2),$$

$$(u_3, 0.4, 0.1, 0.2), (u_4, 0.5, 0.2, 0.15), (u_5, 0.4, 0.2, 0.2)\}.$$

Some basic properties of rough standard neutrosophic set operators are presented in the following theorem:

Theorem 1. Let (U, R) be a crisp approximation space, then the upper and lower rough standard neutrosophic approximation operators satisfy the following properties: $\forall A, B, A_j \in PFS(U)$, $j \in J$, J is an index set,

$$(PL1) \quad \underline{PR}(\sim A) = \sim \overline{RP}(A)$$

$$(PL2) \quad \underline{RP}(A \cup (\alpha, \beta, \theta)) = \underline{RP}(A) \cup (\alpha, \beta, \theta)$$

$$\underline{RP}(A \cup (\widehat{\alpha}, \widehat{\beta}, \widehat{\theta})) = \underline{RP}(A) \cup (\widehat{\alpha}, \widehat{\beta}, \widehat{\theta})$$

$$(PL3) \quad \underline{RP}(U) = U \quad \overline{RP}(U) = U$$

$$\eta_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x) = \bigwedge_{y \in R_s(x)} \eta_A(y)$$

$$(PL5) \quad \underline{RP}(A \cup B) \supseteq \underline{RP}(A) \cup \underline{RP}(B)$$

$$(PL6) \quad A \subseteq B \Rightarrow \underline{RP}(A) \subseteq \underline{RP}(B)$$

$$(PU1) \quad \overline{RP}(\sim A) = \sim \underline{RP}(A) \quad \overline{RP}(\sim A) = \sim \underline{PR}(A)$$

$$(PU2) \quad \overline{PR}(A \cap (\widehat{\alpha}, \widehat{\beta}, \widehat{\theta})) = \overline{PR}(A) \cap (\widehat{\alpha}, \widehat{\beta}, \widehat{\theta})$$

$$(PU3) \quad \overline{PR}(\emptyset) = \emptyset$$

$$(PU4) \quad \overline{RP}(\bigcup_{j \in J} A_j) = \bigcup_{j \in J} \overline{RP}(A_j)$$

$$(PU5) \quad \overline{RP}(A \cap B) \subseteq \overline{RP}(A) \cap \overline{RP}(B)$$

$$(PU6) \quad A \subseteq B \Rightarrow \overline{RP}(A) \subseteq \overline{RP}(B)$$

Proof.

(PL1).

$$\underline{RP}(\sim A) = \{(x, \mu_{\underline{RP}(\sim A)}(x), \eta_{\underline{RP}(\sim A)}(x), \gamma_{\underline{RP}(\sim A)}(x)) \mid x \in U\}$$

in which,

$$\mu_{\underline{RP}(\sim A)}(x) = \bigvee_{y \in R_s(x)} \mu_{\sim A}(y) = \bigvee_{y \in R_s(x)} \gamma_A(y) =$$

$$\gamma_{\overline{RP}(A)}(x);$$

$$\eta_{\underline{RP}(\sim A)}(x) = \bigwedge_{y \in R_s(x)} \eta_{\sim A}(y) = \bigwedge_{y \in R_s(x)} \eta_A(y) =$$

$$\eta_{\overline{RP}(A)}(x)$$

$$\gamma_{\underline{RP}(\sim A)}(x) = \bigwedge_{y \in R_s(x)} \gamma_{\sim A}(y) = \bigwedge_{y \in R_s(x)} \mu_A(y) =$$

$$\mu_{\overline{RP}(A)}(x)$$

From that and lemma 1, we have $\underline{PR}(\sim A) = \sim \overline{RP}(A)$.

(PL2) Because $(\alpha, \beta, \theta) = \{(x, \alpha, \beta, \theta) \mid x \in U\}$, we have

$$\mu_{\underline{RP}(A \cup (\alpha, \beta, \theta))}(x) = \bigvee_{y \in R_s(x)} \mu_{\underline{RP}(A \cup (\alpha, \beta, \theta))}(y)$$

$$\bigvee_{y \in R_s(x)} \mu_{\underline{RP}(A \cup (\alpha, \beta, \theta))}(y) = \bigvee_{y \in R_s(x)} \max\{\mu_{\underline{RP}(A)}(y), \alpha\}$$

$$= \max\{\bigvee_{y \in R_s(x)} \mu_{\underline{RP}(A)}(y), \bigvee_{y \in R_s(x)} \alpha\}$$

$$= \max\{\bigvee_{y \in R_s(x)} \mu_{\underline{RP}(A)}(y), \bigvee_{y \in R_s(x)} \alpha\}$$

$$\max\{\mu_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x), \mu_{((\alpha, \beta, \theta))}(x)\} = \mu_{\underline{RP}(A) \cup (\alpha, \beta, \theta)}(x).$$

By the same way, we have

$$\eta_{\underline{RP}(A \cup (\alpha, \beta, \theta))}(x) = \eta_{\underline{RP}(A \cup (\alpha, \beta, \theta))}(x)$$

and

$$\gamma_{\underline{RP}(A \cup (\alpha, \beta, \theta))}(x) = \gamma_{\underline{RP}(A \cup (\alpha, \beta, \theta))}(x).$$

It means $\underline{RP}(A \cup (\alpha, \beta, \theta)) = \underline{RP}(A) \cup (\alpha, \beta, \theta)$.

(PL3) Since $U = 1_U = (\overline{1,0,0}) = \{(x, 1,0,0) \mid x \in U\}$, then we can obtain (PL3) $\underline{RP}(U) = U$ by using definition 5.

The results (PL4), (PL5), (PL6) were proved by using the definition of lower and upper approximation spaces (definition 5) and lemma 1. $\mu_{\underline{RP}(\overline{(\alpha, \beta, \theta)}}(x)$

Similarly, we have (PU1), (PU2), (PU3), (PU4), (PU5), PU(6). □

Theorem 2. Let (U, R) be a crisp approximation space. Then

a) $\underline{RP}(U) = U = \overline{RP}(U)$ and

$$\underline{RP}(\emptyset) = \emptyset = \overline{RP}(\emptyset) \quad \underline{RP}(\emptyset) = \emptyset = \overline{RP}(\emptyset).$$

b) $\underline{RP}(A) \subseteq \overline{RP}(A)$ for all $A \in \text{PFS}(U)$. □

Proof.

(a) Using (PL3), (PL6), (PU3), (PU6), we easy prove $\underline{RP}(U) = U = \overline{RP}(U)$ and $\underline{RP}(\emptyset) = \emptyset = \overline{RP}(\emptyset)$.

(b) Based on definition 5, we have

$$\mu_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x) = \bigwedge_{y \in R_s(x)} \mu_A(y)$$

$$\leq \mu_{\overline{RP}(A)}(x) = \bigvee_{y \in R_s(x)} \mu_A(y),$$

$$\eta_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x) = \bigwedge_{y \in R_s(x)} \eta_A(y) = \eta_{\overline{RP}(A)}(x),$$

and

$$\gamma_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x) = \bigvee_{y \in R_s(x)} \gamma_A(y) \geq$$

$$\bigwedge_{y \in R_s(x)} \gamma_A(y) = \gamma_{\overline{RP}(A)}(x)$$

So $\underline{RP}(A) \subseteq \overline{RP}(A)$ for all $A \in \text{PFS}(U)$. □

In the case of connections between special types of crisp relation on U, and properties of rough standard neutrosophic approximation operators, we have the following:

Lemma 2. If R is a symmetric crisp binary relation on U, then for all A, B ∈ PFS(U),

$$\overline{RP}(A) \subseteq B \Leftrightarrow A \subseteq \underline{RP}(B)$$

Proof.

Let R be a symmetric crisp binary relation on U, i.e. $y \in R_s(x) \Leftrightarrow x \in R_s(y), \forall x, y \in U$. We assume contradiction that $\overline{RP}(A) \subseteq B$ but $A \not\subseteq \underline{RP}(B)$.

For each $x \in U$, we consider all the cases:

+ if $\mu_A(x) > \mu_{\underline{RP}(B)}(x) = \bigwedge_{y \in R_s(x)} \mu_B(y)$ then it exists $y_0 \in R_s(x)$ such that $\mu_A(x) > \mu_B(y_0) \geq \mu_{\overline{RP}(A)}(y_0) = \bigvee_{z \in R_s(y_0)} \mu_A(z) \geq \mu_A(x)$ (because $y_0 \in R_s(x)$ then $x \in R_s(y_0)$). This is not true.
 + the cases $\gamma_A(x) < \gamma_{\overline{RP}(B)}(x)$ or $\eta_A(x) > \eta_{\overline{RP}(B)}(x)$ are also not true. □

Theorem 3. Let (U, R) be a crisp approximation space, and $\underline{RP}$, the upper and lower PF approximation operators.

Then:

- (a) R is reflexive if and only if at least one of the following conditions are satisfied
 - (a1) (PLR) $\underline{RP}(A) \subseteq A \forall A \in \text{PFS}(U)$
 - (a2) (PUR) $A \subseteq \overline{RP}(A) \forall A \in \text{PFS}(U)$
- (b) R is symmetric if and only if at least one of the following conditions are satisfied
 - (b1) (PLR) $\overline{RP}(\underline{RP}(A)) \subseteq A \forall A \in \text{PFS}(U)$
 - (b2) (PUR) $A \subseteq \underline{RP}(\overline{RP}(A)) \forall A \in \text{PFS}(U)$
- (c) R is transitive if and only if at least one of the following conditions are satisfied
 - (c1) (PLT) $\underline{RP}(A) \subseteq \underline{RP}(\underline{RP}(A)) \forall A \in \text{PFS}(U)$
 - (c2) (PUT) $\overline{RP}(A) \subseteq \overline{RP}(\overline{RP}(A)) \forall A \in \text{PFS}(U)$

Proof.

(a). We assume that R is reflexive, i.e., $x \in R_s(x)$, so that $\forall A \in \text{PFS}(U)$ we have
 $\mu_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x) = \bigwedge_{y \in R_s(x)} \mu_A(y) \leq \mu_A(x)$,
 $\eta_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x) = \bigwedge_{y \in R_s(x)} \mu_A(y) \leq \eta_A(x)$,
 and $\gamma_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x) = \bigvee_{y \in R_s(x)} \gamma_A(y) \geq \gamma_A(x)$. It means that $\underline{RP}(A) \subseteq A$, $\forall A \in \text{PFS}(U)$, i.e. (a1) was verified. Similarly, we consider upper approximation of:
 $\mu_{\overline{RP}(A)}(x) = \bigvee_{y \in R_s(x)} \mu_A(y) \geq \mu_A(x)$, $\eta_{\overline{RP}(A)}(x) = \bigwedge_{y \in R_s(x)} \mu_A(y) = \eta_A(x)$, and $\gamma_{\overline{RP}(A)}(x) = \bigwedge_{y \in R_s(x)} \gamma_A(y) \leq \gamma_A(x)$.

It means $A \subseteq \overline{RP}(A)$, $\forall A \in \text{PFS}(U)$, i.e. (a2) is satisfied.

Now, assume that (a1) $\underline{RP}(A) \subseteq A$, $\forall A \in \text{PFS}(U)$; we show that R is reflexive. Indeed, we assume contradiction that R is not reflexive, i.e. $x \notin R_s(x)$.

We consider $A = 1_{U-\{x\}}$, i.e. $\mu_{1_{U-\{x\}}}(y) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } y = x \\ 1 & \text{if } y \neq x \end{cases}$,
 $\eta_{1_{U-\{x\}}}(y) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } y = x \\ 0 & \text{if } y \neq x \end{cases}$, $\gamma_{1_{U-\{x\}}}(y) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } y = x \\ 0 & \text{if } y \neq x \end{cases}$.

Then $\gamma_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x) = \bigvee_{y \in R_s(x)} \gamma_A(y) = 0 \geq \gamma_A(x) = 1$. This is not true. It implies R is reflexive.

Similarly, we assume that (a2) $A \subseteq \overline{RP}(A)$, $\forall A \in \text{PFS}(U)$; we show that R is reflexive. Indeed, we assume contradiction that R is not reflexive, i.e., $x \notin R_s(x)$.

We consider $A = 1_x$, i.e., $\mu_{1_x}(y) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } y = x \\ 0 & \text{if } y \neq x \end{cases}$,
 $\eta_{1_x}(y) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } y = x \\ 0 & \text{if } y \neq x \end{cases}$, $\gamma_{1_x}(y) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } y = x \\ 1 & \text{if } y \neq x \end{cases}$.

Then $\mu_{\overline{RP}(A)}(x) = \bigvee_{y \in R_s(x)} \mu_A(y) = 0 \geq \mu_A(x) = 1$. This is not true. It implies R is reflexive.

(b).

We verify case (b1). $x \in R_s(y)$
 We assume that R is symmetric, i.e., if $x \in R_s(y)$ then $y \in R_s(x)$. For all $A \in \text{PFS}(U)$, because
 then $\bigwedge_{z \in R_s(y)} \mu_A(z) \leq \mu_A(x)$, $\bigwedge_{z \in R_s(y)} \mu_A(z) \leq \mu_A(x)$, $\bigvee_{z \in R_s(y)} \gamma_A(z) \geq \gamma_A(x)$ for all $y \in R_s(x)$, we have
 $\mu_{\overline{RP}(\underline{RP}(A))}(x) = \bigvee_{y \in R_s(x)} (\bigwedge_{z \in R_s(y)} \mu_A(z)) \leq \mu_A(x)$,
 $\eta_{\overline{RP}(\underline{RP}(A))}(x) = \bigvee_{y \in R_s(x)} (\bigwedge_{z \in R_s(y)} \eta_A(z)) \leq \eta_A(x)$; and
 $\gamma_{\overline{RP}(\underline{RP}(A))}(x) = \bigwedge_{y \in R_s(x)} (\bigvee_{z \in R_s(y)} \gamma_A(z)) \geq \gamma_A(x)$.

It means that $\overline{RP}(\underline{RP}(A)) \subseteq A \quad \forall A \in PFS(U)$.

We assume contradiction that $\overline{RP}(\underline{RP}(A)) \subseteq A \quad \forall A \in PFS(U)$ but R is not symmetric, i.e., if $x \in R_S(y)$ then $y \notin R_S(x)$ and if $y \in R_S(x)$ then $x \notin R_S(y)$.

We consider $A = 1_{U-\{x\}}$. Then, $\mu_{\overline{RP}(\underline{RP}(A))}(x) = \bigvee_{y \in R_S(x)} (\bigwedge_{z \in R_S(y)} \mu_A(z)) = 1 > \mu_A(x) = 0$. It is not true, because $\mu_{\overline{RP}(\underline{RP}(A))}(x) \leq \mu_A(x)$, for all $x \in U$. So that R is symmetric.

By the same way, it yields (b2).

(c). R is transitive, i.e., if for all $x, y, z \in U$: $z \in R_S(y), y \in R_S(x)$ then $z \in R_S(x)$. It means that

$R_S(y) \subseteq R_S(x)$, so that for all $A \in PFS(U)$ we have

$$\bigwedge_{z \in R_S(x)} \mu_A(z) \leq \bigwedge_{z \in R_S(y)} \mu_A(z).$$

Hence

$$\bigwedge_{y \in R_S(x)} (\bigwedge_{z \in R_S(x)} \mu_A(z)) \leq \bigwedge_{y \in R_S(x)} (\bigwedge_{z \in R_S(y)} \mu_A(z)).$$

Because $\mu_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x) = \bigwedge_{y \in R_S(x)} (\bigwedge_{z \in R_S(x)} \mu_A(z))$

and $\mu_{\underline{RP}(\underline{RP}(A))}(x) = \bigwedge_{y \in R_S(x)} (\bigwedge_{z \in R_S(y)} \mu_A(z))$.

So $\mu_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x) \leq \mu_{\underline{RP}(\underline{RP}(A))}(x)$, for all $x \in U, A \in PFS(U)$.

It mean that (c1) was varified. Now, we assume contradiction that (c1): $\overline{RP}(A) \subseteq \overline{RP}(\overline{RP}(A)) \forall A \in PFS(U)$,

but R is not transitive, i.e., $x, y, z \in U$:

$z \in R_S(y), y \in R_S(x)$ then $z \notin R_S(x)$. We consider

$A = 1_{U-\{x\}}$, then $\mu_{\underline{RP}(A)}(x) = \bigwedge_{z \in R_S(x)} \mu_A(z) = 1$, but

$$\mu_{\underline{RP}(\underline{RP}(A))}(x) = \bigwedge_{y \in R_S(x)} (\bigwedge_{z \in R_S(y)} \mu_A(z)) = 0.$$

It is false. By same way, we show that (c2) is true. Hence, (c) was verified.□

Now, according to Theorem 1, Lemma 1 and Theorem 3, we obtain the following results:

Theorem 4. Let R be a similarity crisp binary relation on U and $\overline{RP}, \underline{RP}: PFS(U) \rightarrow PFS(U)$ the upper and lower PF approximation operators. Then, for all $A \in PFS(U)$

$$A = \underline{RP}(A) - \overline{RP}(A) = A$$

$$- \quad \sim A = \underline{RP}(\sim A) \Leftrightarrow \overline{RP}(\sim A) = \sim A.$$

4. The standard neutrosophic information systems

In this section, we introduce a new concept: standard neutrosophic information system.

Let (U, A, F) be a classical information system. Here U is the (nonempty) set of objects, i.e. $U = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$, $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_m\}$ is the attribute set, and F is the relation set of U and A , i.e. $F = \{f_j: U \rightarrow V_j, j = 1, 2, \dots, m\}$, where V_j is the domain of the attribute $a_j, j = 1, 2, \dots, m$.

We call (U, A, F, D, G) an information system or decision table, where (U, A, F) is the classical information system, A is the condition attribute set and D is the decision attribute set, i.e. $D = \{d_1, d_2, \dots, d_p\}$ and G is the relation set of U and D , i.e. $G = \{g_j: U \rightarrow V_j, j = 1, 2, \dots, p\}$ where V_j is the domain of the attribute $d_j, j = 1, 2, \dots, p$.

Let (U, A, F, D, G) be the information system. For $B \subseteq A \cup D$, we define a relation, denoted $R_B = IND(B)$, as follows, $\forall x, y \in U$:

$$xIND(B)y \Leftrightarrow f_j(x) = f_j(y) \text{ for all } j \in \{j: a_j \in B\}.$$

The equivalence class of $x \in U$ based on R_B is $[x]_B = \{y \in U: yR_Bx\}$.

Here, we consider $R_A = IND(A), R_D = IND(D)$. If $R_A \subseteq R_D, R_A \subseteq R_D$, i.e., for any $[x]_A, x \in U$ there exists $[x]_D$ such that $[x]_A \subseteq [x]_D$, then the information system is called a consistent information system, other called an inconsistent information system.

Let (U, A, F, D, G) be the information system, where (U, A, F) is a classical information system.

If $D = \{D_k | k = 1, 2, \dots, q\}$, where D_k is a fuzzy subset of U , then (U, A, F, D, G) is the fuzzy information system.

If $D = \{D_k | k = 1, 2, \dots, q\}$ where D_k is an intuitionistic fuzzy subset of U , then (U, A, F, D, G) is an intuitionistic fuzzy information system.

Definition 6. Let (U, A, F, D, G) be the information system or decision table, where (U, A, F) is a classical information system. If $D = \{D_k | k = 1, 2, \dots, q\}$, where D_k is a standard neutrosophic subset of U , and G is the relation set of U and D , then (U, A, F, D, G) is called a standard neutrosophic information system.

Example 2. The following Table 2 gives a standard neutrosophic information system, where the objects set $U = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{10}\}$, the condition attribute set is $A = \{a_1, a_2, a_3\}$, and the decision attribute set is $D = \{D_1, D_2, D_3\}$, where $D_k (k = 1, 2, 3)$ is the standard neutrosophic subsets of U .

Table 2: A standard neutrosophic information system

U	a_1	a_2	a_3	D_1	D_2	D_3
u_1	3	2	1	(0.2,0.3,0.5)	(0.15,0.6,0.2)	(0.4,0.05,0.5)
u_2	1	3	2	(0.3,0.1,0.5)	(0.3,0.3,0.3)	(0.35,0.1,0.4)
u_3	3	2	1	(0.6,0,0.4)	(0.3,0.05,0.6)	(0.1,0.45,0.4)
u_4	3	3	1	(0.15,0.1,0.7)	(0.1,0.05,0.8)	(0.2,0.4,0.3)
u_5	2	2	4	(0.05,0.2,0.7)	(0.2,0.4,0.3)	(0.05,0.4,0.5)
u_6	2	3	4	(0.1,0.3,0.5)	(0.2,0.3,0.4)	(1,0,0)
u_7	1	3	2	(0.25,0.3,0.4)	(1,0,0)	(0.3,0.3,0.4)
u_8	2	2	4	(0.1,0.6,0.2)	(0.25,0.3,0.4)	(0.4,0,0.6)
u_9	3	2	1	(0.45,0.1,0.45)	(0.25,0.4,0.3)	(0.2,0.5,0.3)
u_{10}	1	3	2	(0.05,0.05,0.9)	(0.4,0.2,0.3)	(0.05,0.7,0.2)

5. The knowledge discovery in the standard neutrosophic information systems

In this section, we will give some results about the knowledge discovery for a standard neutrosophic information systems by using the basic theory of rough standard neutrosophic set in Section 3. Throughout this paper, let (U, A, F, D, G) be the standard neutrosophic information system and by $B \subseteq A$, we denote $\underline{RP}_B(D_j)$ the lower rough standard neutrosophic approximation of $D_j \in PFS(U)$ on approximation space (U, R_B) .

Theorem 5. Let (U, A, F, D, G) be the standard neutrosophic information system and $B \subseteq A$. If for any $x \in U$:

$$(\mu_{D_i}(x), \eta_{D_i}(x), \gamma_{D_i}(x)) \geq (\alpha(x), \beta(x), \theta(x))$$

$$= \underline{RP}_B(D_i)(x) > \underline{RP}_B(D_j)(x) (i \neq j),$$

$$\text{then } [x]_B \cap (\sim D_j)_{\alpha(x)}^{\beta(x),0} \neq \emptyset \quad [x]_B \cap (\sim D_j)_{\alpha(x)}^{\beta(x),0} \neq \emptyset$$

$$[x]_B \cap (\sim D_j)_{\alpha(x)}^{\theta(x),0} \neq \emptyset \quad [x]_B \cap (\sim D_j)_{\alpha(x)}^{\theta(x),0} \neq \emptyset \quad \text{and}$$

$$[x]_B \subseteq (D_i)_{\theta(x)}^{\alpha(x),\beta(x)} \quad [x]_B \cap (\sim D_j)_{\alpha(x)}^{\beta(x),0} \neq \emptyset [x]_B \subseteq$$

$$(D_i)_{\beta(x)}^{\alpha(x),\theta(x)} [x]_B \cap (\sim D_j)_{\alpha(x)}^{\beta(x),0} \neq \emptyset$$

where $(\alpha(x), \beta(x), \theta(x)) \in D^*$.

Proof.

We have

$$(D_i)_{\theta(x)}^{\alpha(x),\beta(x)} = \{y \in U : (\mu_{D_i}(y), \eta_{D_i}(y), \gamma_{D_i}(y))$$

$$\geq (\alpha(x), \beta(x), \theta(x))\}.$$

Since $(\alpha(x), \beta(x), \theta(x)) = \underline{RP}_B(D_i)(x)$,

we have $\alpha(x) = \wedge_{y \in [x]_B} \mu_{D_i}(y)$, $\beta(x) = \wedge_{y \in [x]_B} \eta_{D_i}(y)$,

and $\theta(x) = \vee_{y \in [x]_B} \gamma_{D_i}(y)$. So that, for any $x \in U, y \in [x]_B$

then $\mu_{D_i}(y) \geq \alpha(x)$, $\eta_{D_i}(y) \geq \theta(x)$ $\gamma_{D_i}(y) \leq \theta(x)$ and

$\eta_{D_i}(y) \geq \theta(x)$. It means that $y \in (D_i)_{\theta(x)}^{\alpha(x),\beta(x)}$, i.e.,

$$[x]_B \subseteq (D_i)_{\theta(x)}^{\alpha(x),\beta(x)} [x]_B \subseteq (D_i)_{\theta(x)}^{\alpha(x),\beta(x)}$$

Now, since

$$(\alpha(x), \beta(x), \theta(x)) = \underline{RP}_B(D_i)(x) > \underline{RP}_B(D_j)(x) (i \neq j)$$

then there exists $y \in [x]_B$ such that

$$(\mu_{D_i}(y), \eta_{D_i}(y), \gamma_{D_i}(y)) < (\alpha(x), \beta(x), \theta(x))$$

$(\mu_{D_i}(y), \eta_{D_i}(y), \gamma_{D_i}(y)) < (\alpha(x), \beta(x), \theta(x))$ i.e., or

$(\mu_{D_i}(y) < \alpha(x), \gamma_{D_i}(y) \geq \theta(x))$ or $(\mu_{D_i}(y) = \alpha(x),$

$\gamma_{D_i}(y) > \theta(x))$ or $(\mu_{D_i}(y) = \alpha(x), \gamma_{D_i}(y) > \theta(x))$ and

$\eta_{D_i}(y) < \beta(x)$. It means that here exists $y \in [x]_B$ such that

$(\gamma_{D_i}(y), \eta_{D_i}(y), \mu_{D_i}(y)) \geq (\theta(x), 0, \alpha(x))$, i.e. $y \in (\sim$

$D_j)_{\alpha(x)}^{\theta(x),0}$. So that $[x]_B \cap (\sim D_j)_{\alpha(x)}^{\theta(x),0} \neq \emptyset$.

Let (U, A, F, D, G) be the standard neutrosophic information system, R_A the equivalence classes which are induced by the condition attribute set A , and the universe is divided by R_A as following: $U/R_A = \{X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k\}$. Then the approximation of the standard neutrosophic decision denoted as, for all $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$

$$\underline{RP}_A(D(X_i)) = (\underline{RP}_A(D_1(X_i)), \underline{RP}_A(D_2(X_i)), \dots, \underline{RP}_A(D_q(X_i)))$$

Example 3. We consider the standard neutrosophic information system in Table 2. The equivalent classes

$$U / R_A = \{X_1 = \{u_1, u_3, u_9\}, X_2 = \{u_2, u_7, u_{10}\},$$

$$X_3 = \{u_4\}, X_4 = \{u_5, u_8\}, X_5 = \{u_6\}\}$$

The approximation of the standard neutrosophic decision is as follows:

Table 3: The approximation of the picture fuzzy decision

U / R_A	$\underline{RP}_A(D_1(X_i))$	$\underline{RP}_A(D_2(X_i))$	$\underline{RP}_A(D_3(X_i))$
X_1	(0.2,0,0.5)	(0.15,0.05,0.6)	(0.1,0.05,0.5)
X_2	(0.05,0.05,0.9)	(0.3,0.1,0.3)	(0.05,0.1,0.4)
X_3	(0.15, 0.1,0.7)	(0.1,0.05,0.8)	(0.2,0.4,0.3)
X_4	(0.05,0.2,0.7)	(0.2,0.3,0.4)	(0.05,0,0.6)
X_5	(0.1,0.3,0.5)	(0.2,0.3,0.4)	(1,0,0)

Indeed, for $X_1 = \{u_1, u_3, u_9\}$.

We have $\forall x \in X_1$,

$$\mu_{\underline{RP}_A(D_1)}(x) = \wedge_{y \in X_1} \mu_{D_1}(y) = \min\{0.2, 0.6, 0.45\} = 0.2,$$

$$\eta_{\underline{RP}_A(D_1)}(x) = \wedge_{y \in X_1} \eta_{D_1}(y) = \min\{0.3, 0, 0.1\} = 0$$

$$\gamma_{\underline{RP}_A(D_1)}(x) = \vee_{y \in X_1} \gamma_{D_1}(y) = \max\{0.5, 0.4, 0.45\} = 0.5,$$

$y \in (\sim D_j)_{\alpha(x)}^{\beta(x),0}$, so that $\underline{RP}_A(D_1)(x) = (0.2, 0.5, 0)$. And

$$\mu_{\underline{RP}_A(D_2)}(x) = \wedge_{y \in X_1} \mu_{D_2}(y) = \min\{0.15, 0.3, 0.25\} = 0.15,$$

$$\eta_{\underline{RP}_A(D_2)}(x) = \wedge_{y \in X_1} \eta_{D_2}(y) = \min\{0.6, 0.05, 0.4\} = 0.05,$$

$$\gamma_{\underline{RP}_A(D_2)}(x) = \vee_{y \in X_1} \gamma_{D_2}(y) = \max\{0.2, 0.6, 0.3\} = 0.6$$

so $\underline{RP}_A(D_2)(x) = (0.15, 0.6, 0.05)$ and

$$\mu_{\underline{RP}_A(D_3)}(x) = \wedge_{y \in X_1} \mu_{D_3}(y) = \min\{0.4, 0.1, 0.2\} = 0.1,$$

$$\eta_{\underline{RP}_A(D_3)}(x) = \wedge_{y \in X_1} \eta_{D_3}(y) = \min\{0.05, 0.45, 0.5\} = 0.05,$$

$$\gamma_{\underline{RP}_A(D_3)}(x) = \vee_{y \in X_1} \gamma_{D_3}(y) = \max\{0.5, 0.2, 0.3\} = 0.5$$

so that $\underline{RP}_A(D_3)(x) = (0.1, 0.5, 0.05)$.

Hence, for $X_1 = \{u_1, u_3, u_9\}$, $\forall x \in X_2$,

$$\max_{i=\{1,2,3\}} \underline{RP}_A(D_i)(x) =$$

$$\underline{RP}_A(D_1)(x) = (0.2, 0.5, 0), \max_{i=\{1,2,3\}} \underline{RP}_A(D_i)(x) =$$

$$\text{and } X_1 = \{u_1, u_3, u_9\} \subseteq (D_1)_{0.5}^{0.2,0} = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, u_7, u_9\};$$

For $X_2 = \{u_2, u_7, u_{10}\}$. We have $\forall x \in X_2$,

$$\max_{i=\{1,2,3\}} \underline{RP}_A(D_i)(x) = \underline{RP}_A(D_2)(x) = (0.3, 0.3, 0.1),$$

$$\text{and } X_2 = \{u_2, u_7, u_{10}\} \subseteq (D_2)_{0.3}^{0.3,0.1} = \{u_2, u_7, u_{10}\}.$$

For $X_3 = \{u_4\}$, we have $\forall x \in X_2$,

$$\max_{i=\{1,2,3\}} \underline{RP}_A(D_i)(x) = \underline{RP}_A(D_3)(x) = (0.2, 0.3, 0.4),$$

$$\text{and } X_3 = \{u_4\} \subseteq (D_2)_{0.3}^{0.3,0.1} = \{u_4, u_6, u_9\} X_3 = \{u_4\} \subseteq (D_2)_{0.3}^{0.3,0.1} = \{u_4, u_6, u_9\}.$$

For $X_3 = \{u_4\}$, we have $\forall x \in X_2$

$$\max_{i=\{1,2,3\}} \underline{RP}_A(D_i)(x) = \underline{RP}_A(D_3)(x) = (0.2, 0.3, 0.4)$$

$$\text{and } X_4 = \{u_5, u_8\} \subseteq (D_2)_{0.4}^{0.2,0.3} = \{u_2, u_5, u_8, u_9, u_{10}\}$$

$$X_4 = \{u_5, u_8\} \subseteq (D_2)_{0.4}^{0.2,0.3} = \{u_2, u_5, u_8, u_9, u_{10}\}.$$

For $X_3 = \{u_4\}$, we have $\forall x \in X_2$,

$$\max_{i=\{1,2,3\}} \underline{RP}_A(D_i)(x) = \underline{RP}_A(D_3)(x) = (0.2, 0.3, 0.4), \text{ and}$$

$$X_5 = \{u_6\} \subseteq (D_2)_0^{1,0} = \{u_6\}.$$

6 The knowledge reduction and extension of standard neutrosophic information systems

Definition 7.

(i) Let (U, A, F) (U, A, F) be the classical information system and $B \subseteq A$. B is called the standard neutrosophic reduction of the classical information system (U, A, F) , if B is the minimum set which satisfies the following relations: for any $X \in \text{PFS}(U)$, $x \in U$.

$$\underline{RP}_A(X) = \underline{RP}_B(X), \overline{RP}_A(X) = \overline{RP}_B(X)$$

(ii) B is called the standard neutrosophic lower approximation reduction of the classical information system (U, A, F) , if B is the minimum set which satisfies the following relations: for any $X \in \text{PFS}(U)$, $x \in U$

$$\underline{RP}_A(X) = \underline{RP}_B(X),$$

(iii) B is called the standard neutrosophic upper approximation reduction of the classical information system (U, A, F) , if B is the minimum set which satisfies the following relations: for any $X \in \text{PFS}(U)$, $x \in U$

$$\overline{RP}_A(X) = \overline{RP}_B(X)$$

where $\underline{RP}_A(X), \underline{RP}_B(X), \overline{RP}_A(X), \overline{RP}_B(X)$

$\underline{RP}_A(X), \underline{RP}_B(X), \overline{RP}_A(X), \overline{RP}_B(X)$ are standard neutro-

sophic lower and standard neutrosophic upper approximation sets of standard neutrosophic set $X \in \text{PFS}(U)$ based on $R_A, R_B, R_{R_A}, R_{R_B}$, respectively.

Now, we express the knowledge of the reduction of standard neutrosophic information system by introducing the discernibility matrix.

Definition 8. Let (U, A, F, D, G) be the standard neutrosophic information system. Then $M = [D_{ij}]_{k \times k}$ where

$$D_{ij} = \begin{cases} \{a_i \in A : f_i(X_i) \neq f_i(X_j)\}; & g_{X_i}(D_i) \neq g_{X_j}(D_j) \\ A & ; g_{X_i}(D_i) = g_{X_j}(D_j) \end{cases}$$

is called the discernibility matrix of (U, A, F, D, G) (where $g_{X_i}(D_k)$ is the maximum of $\underline{RP}_A(D(X_i))$ obtained at D_i, D_k , i.e., $g_{X_i}(D_i) = \underline{RP}_A(D_i(X_i))$)

$$= \max\{\underline{RP}_A(D_z(X_i)), z = 1, 2, \dots, q\} g_{X_i}(D_k) = \underline{RP}_A(D_k(X_i)) = \max\{\underline{RP}_A(D_t(X_i)), t = 1, 2, \dots, q\}.$$

Definition 9. Let (U, A, F, D, G) be the standard neutrosophic information system, for any $B \subseteq A$, if the following relations holds, for any $x \in U$:

$$\underline{RP}_B(D_i)(x) > \underline{RP}_B(D_j)(x) - \underline{RP}_A(D_i)(x) > \underline{RP}_A(D_j)(x) (i \neq j)$$

then B is called the consistent set of A .

Theorem 6. Let (U, A, F, D, G) be the standard neutrosophic information system. If there exists a subset $B \subseteq A$ such that $B \cap D_{ij} \neq \emptyset$, then B is the consistent set of A .

Definition 10. Let (U, A, F, D, G) be the standard neutrosophic information system

$$D_{ij}^C = \begin{cases} \{a_i \in A : f_i(X_i) = f_i(X_j)\}; & g_{X_i}(D_i) \neq g_{X_j}(D_j) \\ \emptyset & ; g_{X_i}(D_i) = g_{X_j}(D_j) \end{cases}$$

is called the discernibility matrix of (U, A, F, D, G) (where $g_{X_i}(D_k)$ is the maximum of $\underline{RP}_A(D(X_i))$ obtained at D_k , i.e.

$$g_{X_i}(D_i) = \underline{RP}_A(D_i(X_i)) = \max\{\underline{RP}_A(D_z(X_i)), z = 1, 2, \dots, q\}.$$

$$g_{X_i}(D_k) = \underline{RP}_A(D_k(X_i)) = \max\{\underline{RP}_A(D_t(X_i)), t = 1, 2, \dots, q\}.$$

Theorem 7. Let (U, A, F, D, G) be the standard neutrosophic information system. If there exists a subset

$B \subseteq A$ such that $B \cap D_{ij}^C = \emptyset$, then B is the consistent set of A .

Proof. If $B \cap D_{ij}^C = \emptyset$, then $B \subseteq D_{ij}$. According to Theorem 6, B is the consistent set of A . $\square$

The extension of a standard neutrosophic information system suggested the following definition:

Definition 11.

(i) Let (U, A, F) be the classical information system and $A \subseteq B$. B is called the standard neutrosophic extension of the classical information system (U, A, F) , if B satisfies the following relations:

for any $X \in \text{PFS}(U), x \in U$

$$\underline{RP}_A(X) = \underline{RP}_B(X), \overline{RP}_A(X) = \overline{RP}_B(X)$$

(ii) B is called the standard neutrosophic lower approximation extension of the classical information system (U, A, F) , if B satisfies the following relations:

for any $X \in \text{PFS}(U), x \in U$

$$\underline{RP}_A(X) = \underline{RP}_B(X)$$

(iii) B is called the standard neutrosophic upper approximation extension of the classical information system (U, A, F) , if B satisfies the following relations:

for any $X \in \text{PFS}(U), x \in U$

$$\overline{RP}_A(X) = \overline{RP}_B(X)$$

where $\underline{RP}_A(X), \underline{RP}_B(X), \overline{RP}_A(X), \overline{RP}_B(X)$ are picture fuzzy lower and upper approximation sets of standard neutrosophic set $X \in \text{PFS}(U)$ based on R_A, R_B , respectively.

We can easily obtain the following results:

Definition 12. Let (U, A, F) be the classical information system, for any hyper set B , such that $A \subseteq B$, if A is the standard neutrosophic reduction of the classical information system (U, B, F) , then (U, B, F) is the standard neutrosophic extension of (U, A, F) , but not conversely necessary.

Example 4. In the approximation of the standard neutrosophic decision in Table 2, Table 3. Let $B = \{a_1, a_2\}$, then we obtain the family of all equivalent classes of U based on the equivalent relation $R_B = \text{IND}(B)$ as follows:

$$U / R_B = \{X_1 = \{u_1, u_3, u_6\}, X_2 = \{u_2, u_7, u_{10}\}, X_3 = \{u_4\}, X_4 = \{u_5, u_8\}, X_5 = \{u_6\}\}$$

We can get the approximation value given in Table 4.

Table 4: The approximation of the standard neutrosophic decision

U / R_B	$RP_B(D_1(X_i))$	$RP_B(D_2(X_i))$	$RP_B(D_3(X_i))$
X_1	(0.2,0,0.5)	(0.15,0.05,0.6)	(0.1,0.05,0.5)
X_2	(0.05,0.05,0.9)	(0.3,0.1,0.3)	(0.05,0.1,0.4)
X_3	(0.15, 0.1,0.7)	(0.1,0.05,0.8)	(0.2,0.4,0.3)
X_4	(0.05,0.2,0.7)	(0.2,0.3,0.4)	(0.05,0,0.6)
X_5	(0.1,0.3,0.5)	(0.2,0.3,0.4)	(1,0,0)

It is easy to see that B satisfies Definition 7 (ii), i.e., B is the standard neutrosophic lower reduction of the classical information system (U, A, F) .

The discernibility matrix of the standard neutrosophic information system (U, A, F, D, G) will be presented in Table 5.

Table 5: The discernibility matrix of the standard neutrosophic information system

U/R_B	X_1	X_2	X_3	X_4	X_5
X_1	A				
X_2	A	A			
X_3	$\{a_2\}$	$\{a_1, a_3\}$	A		
X_4	$\{a_1, a_3\}$	A	A	A	
X_5	$\{a_1, a_3\}$	A	A	$\{a_2\}$	A

7 Conclusion

In this paper, we introduced the concept of standard neutrosophic information system, and studied the knowledge discovery of standard neutrosophic information system based on rough standard neutrosophic sets. We investigated some problems of the knowledge discovery of standard neutrosophic information system: the knowledge reduction and extension of the standard neutrosophic information systems.

Acknowledgment

This research is funded by the Vietnam National Foundation for Science and Technology Development (NAFOSTED) under grant number 102.01-2017.02 .

References

[1] Z. Pawlak, *Rough sets*, International Journal of Computer and Information Sciences, vol. 11, no.5 , pp 341 – 356, 1982.

[2] L. A. Zadeh, *Fuzzy Sets*, Information and Control, Vol. 8, No. 3 (1965), p 338-353

[3] K. Atanassov, *Intuitionistic fuzzy sets*, Fuzzy set and systems, vol.20, pp.87-96, 1986.

[4] B.C. Cuong, V. Kreinovich, *Picture fuzzy sets – a new concept for computational intelligence problems*, in the Proceedings of the 3rd World congress on information and communication technologies WICT’2013, Hanoi, Vietnam, December 15-18, pp 1-6, 2013.

[5] B.C. Cuong, *Picture Fuzzy Sets*, Journal of Computer Science and Cybernetics, Vol.30, n.4, 2014, 409-420.

[6] B.C. Cuong, P.H.Phong and F. Smarandache, *Standard Neutrosophic Soft Theory: Some First Results*, Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, vol.12, 2016, pp.80-91.

[7] L.H. Son, *DPFCM: A novel distributed picture fuzzy clustering method on picture fuzzy sets*, Expert systems with applications 42, pp 51-66, 2015.

[8] P.H. Thong and L.H.Son, *Picture Fuzzy Clustering : A New Computational Intelligence Method*, Soft Computing, v.20 (9) 3544-3562, 2016.

[9] D. Dubois, H. Prade, *Rough fuzzy sets and fuzzy rough sets*, International journal of general systems, Vol. 17, p 191-209, 1990.

[10] Y.Y. Yao, *Combination of rough and fuzzy sets based on α -level sets*, Rough sets and Data mining: analysis for imprecise data, Kluwer Academic Publisher, Boston, p 301 – 321, 1997.

[11] W. Z. Wu, J. S. Mi, W. X. Zhang, *Generalized fuzzy rough sets*, Information Sciences 151, p. 263-282, 2003.

[12] W. Z. Wu, Y. H. Xu, *On fuzzy topological structures of rough fuzzy sets*, Transactions on rough sets XVI, LNCS 7736, Springer – Verlag Berlin Heidelberg, p 125-143, 2013.

[13] Y.H. Xu, W.Z. Wu, *Intuitionistic fuzzy topologies in crisp approximation spaces*, RSKT 2012, LNAI 7414, © Springer – Verlag Berlin Heidelberg, pp 496-503, 2012.

[14] B. Davvaz, M. Jafarzadeh, *Rough intuitionistic fuzzy information systems*, Fuzzy Inform., vol.4, pp 445-458, 2013.

[15] N.X. Thao, N.V. Dinh, *Rough picture fuzzy set and picture fuzzy topologies*, Science computer and Cybernetics, Vol 31, No 3 (2015), pp 245-254.

[16] B. Sun, Z. Gong, *Rough fuzzy set in generalized approximation space*, Fifth Int. Conf. on Fuzzy Systems and Knowledge Discovery, IEEE computer society 2008, pp 416-420.

[17] F. Smarandache, *A unifying field in logics. Neutrosophy: Neutrosophic probability, set and logic*, ARP, Rehoboth 1999.

[18] H. Wang, F. Smarandache, Y.Q. Zhang et al., *Interval neutrosophic sets and logic: Theory and applications in computing*, Hexis, Phoenix, AZ 2005.

[19] H. Wang, F. Smarandache, Y.Q. Zhang, et al., *Single valued neutrosophic sets*, Multispace & Multistructure 4 (2010), 410-413.

- [20] J. Ye, *A multicriteria decision-making method using aggregation operators for simplified neutrosophic sets*, Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems 26 (2014) 2459-2466.
- [21] P. Majumdar, *Neutrosophic sets and its applications to decision making*, Computation intelligence for big data analysis (2015), V.19, pp 97-115.
- [22] J. Peng, J. Q. Wang, J. Wang, H. Zhang, X. Chen, *Simplified neutrosophic sets and their applications in multi-criteria group decision-making problems*, International journal of systems science (2016), V.47, issue 10, pp 2342-2358.

Received: December 7, 2016. Accepted: December 21, 2016